

The Effect of Internal Control System on Financial Performance (Case Study Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu-Somalia)

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the effect of internal control systems and financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu Somalia. Internal control systems were looked at from the perspective of control environment, control activities and internal audit whereas financial performance focused on liquidity, profitability, market share and financial reporting as the measures of financial performance. The research was conducted using quantitative approaches using Correlation as Research Designs. Stratified and simple random samplings were also applied to collect data. Data was collected using questionnaire and interview as well as review of available documents and records targeting basically top managements, line manager/supervisors and operational staff as respondents from a population of 100 Dahabshil remittance company as sample size of 80. Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientists. The findings generally revealed that there is a significant relationship between control environment on financial performance [$r = 98.8\%$ $P = .000$]. The other remaining of 1.2% may be attributed to other factors indicates that the most contributed factor. The researcher found that management of the remittance is committed to the control systems, actively participates in monitoring and supervision of the activities of the Company in all the activities of the remittance were initiated by the top level management. The researcher also found that the internal audit department is understaffed, doesn't conduct regular audit activities and doesn't produce regular audit reports although the few reports produced by the internal audit department address weaknesses in the system.

Keywords: Internal control system, Financial performance, internal audit, control environment, Control activities, financial Report, Profitability. Liquidity, Remittance. Market Share.

Introduction

Internal control systems as global phenomena are perceived an important tool to ensuring that the organization is run in an efficient manner. An effective internal control system is meant to boost the financial performance through gaining a large market share, profitability and preparation of proper financial reporting in order to satisfy the stakeholders of the organization (Amudo and Inanga, 2009).

Internal control is broadly defined as a process, affected by an entity's board of directors, management and other personnel, designed to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of objectives in the following categories; effectiveness and efficiency of operations, reliability of financial reporting and compliance with applicable laws and regulations (Donald and Delno 2009).

Internal control can help an entity achieve its performance and profitability targets, and prevent loss of resources. It can help ensure reliable financial reporting. And it can help ensure that the enterprise complies with laws and regulations, avoiding damage to its reputation and other consequences. In sum, it can help an entity get to where it wants to go, and avoid pitfalls and surprises along the way (Jenning 2008).

According to Lyman and Carles (2008) defines financial performance is viewed in terms of planning and forecasting, coordinating and controlling, financing, cost analysis, asset management, credits and collection, insurance. On other hand financial report is a process of decision making which involves minimizing losses from both bad debts and costs of debt operation while maximizing the value of shareholder wealth.

The study is an investigation on effects of internal control systems on financial performance in Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu-Somalia. An internal control system is the independent variable while financial performance is dependent variable.

In United States in 1992, a group of companies sponsored the formation of the tread way commission to study and report on how to improve the effectiveness of internal control systems, and more recently in 2002 the US congress passed the Sarbanes Oxley act giving new directives on how companies are to report on the effectiveness or otherwise of their internal control systems. Almost all the managers of the financial institutions within the developed countries were strengthen the internal control system especially after the collapse of the leaded companies for instance Enron, General Motor in USA and other.

Tanzania as a developing nation tries to strengthen the internal control system, through their agencies such as the Central Bank. The Ministry for finance encourages the financial institutions to emphases on implementation of effective internal control system. The board of directors of every financial institutions shall approve proper policies and procedures, and adequate overall internal control systems, for monitoring and controlling the risks for each line of business and market served by such bank or financial institution, including credit, financial, market, operations, legal and any other risk affecting or likely to affect such bank or financial institution (BAFIA, 2006).

(COSO, 2011). An organization without internal control means that organization would be without control toward its desired target, and would soon fall of course, away from the company's objective.

David (2001) defines internal controls as processes designed and affected by those charged with governance,

management, and other personnel to provide reasonable assurance about the achievement of an entity's objectives with regard to reliability of the financial reporting, effectiveness and efficiency of operations and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. Increasingly, reliability of financial reporting in accounting context is very important for the investors who use the information for decision management. The reliability of financial reporting is effective to internal control efficiency to ensure that the transactions and bookkeeping are appropriate and properly authorized, valid, correctly recorded, complete, and on time. Moreover, it is very important that organizations have fairly summarized accounting information data disclosure (Sebbowa, 2009). There is a general perception that institution and enforcement of proper internal control systems always lead to improved financial performance.

According to Kloot, (1999) financial performance is measured in terms of customer satisfaction, profitability, market share through reduced customer complaints. In order to be able to perform organizations should critically look at customers and all stakeholders in business and know how best they are satisfying their needs. Internal control system is intervened with organization's operating activities and it is most effective when controls are built into the organization's infrastructure, becoming organization's part of the very essence of the organizations success in terms of continued improvement on performance standards as part of the competitive advantage of the organization.

Dahabshil Remittance Company is one of the largest remittance operating financial institutions in Somalia. It have filled a major gap that has emerged since the collapse of the country's central government, providing basic banking services and providing a vital channel for the transmission of money among different regions of the country and international countries. Dahabshil remittance has large proportion of Somali society depending on its services. On the other hand it ensures sustainable human development through poverty reduction, capacity building, job creation and institutional strengthening and has designed initiative policies to assist Somali remittance companies in formalizing their operations to ensure continued existence (Abdullah, 2011). Management of Dahabshil Remittance Company made efforts and they were spending a lot of the company budget in the last four years to ensure effective internal control systems with the purpose of improving liquidity, profitability and gaining new market share. Therefore this study investigated the effect of internal control systems on the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company.

Materials and methods

The procedures used by a researcher to explore relationships between variables to form subjects into groups, administer treatments and analyze data. This study employed correlation design.

A correlation study is a quantitative method of research in which you have two or more quantitative variables from the same group of subjects is examined to determine if there is a relationship (or co-variation) between the two variables. The purpose of using a correlation study is to analyze whether there is a relationship between independent variable and dependent variable.

The study relied mostly on primary and secondary data was collected by semi-structured questionnaires with close-ended and non-structured questionnaires (interview).

According to Amin, (2005), Validity refers to the ability of the instrument to collect justifiable and truthful data i.e. it's an important to determining whether the statements in the questionnaires are relevant to the study and therefore it's about soundness or effectiveness of study instruments. The researcher used content validity to enhance the quality of the study.

According to Amin (2005), content validity is the extent to which the items in the instrument represent the content of the attribute being measured and it's highly advised in testing for validity of any research in controlling statement in the instruments, in order to ensure that the tool used was valid, the researcher consulted with the study supervisor to ensure the relevance of the questionnaire and the draft of questionnaires was subjected to scrutiny by five individual experts to evaluate whether each question in the questionnaire is fundamental and valuable. They were asked to assess the validity of questions in the questionnaire by ranking them from one to two against objectives of the study. Scale 1 represented "Not relevant" and 2 stood for „relevant“. Content Validity Index (CVI) was calculated manually and it gave the CVI as 0.836 and is calculated as follows:

Content validity index

No. panel	Number of all relevant questions	Total questions
1	41	49
2	39	49
3	42	49
4	40	49
5	43	49
Total	205	245

So, $205/245 = 0.836$

Thus, the CVI was accepted because normally it should greater than 0.5 ($CVI \geq 0.5$) and preferably greater than 0.7. The CVI of 0.836 showed that the questionnaire was worth to be administered.

Reliability of the instrument. According to Yogesh (2006) defines reliability defined as the degree of data collection method will result in constant findings. It is referred to as reliability if the results of a study can be reproduced under a similar methodology, and then the research instrument is considered to be reliable. To test the reliability of the questionnaire the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The reliability of the questions used to collect data for the analysis of the effect of internal control system on financial performance of Dahabshil remittance company in Mogadishu was 0.946 which implied that the instrument was 94.6% reliable for data collection which is the above the acceptable minimum of 50%. This indicates that the questionnaire was reliable and this yielded similar results and conclusion of this study can be used to make decisions. The researcher computed the reliability using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Table3.3 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.946	49

Source: Primary data

The researcher aimed at organizing data by editing, coding, tabulation and classification, categorizing and correlating data to respective research questions for the major aim of developing valid conclusions and recommendations drawn from the data sets comprising internal control system and financial performance, with support from SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). The frequency and percentage distribution was used to determine the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The researcher used inferential statistical tools to analyze the study, particularly the researcher employed correlation and regression analysis in order to test if there is significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Null hypothesis one: There is no relationship between control environment and the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu

In attempt to test whether there is no relationship between control environment and the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company. The researcher looked at the effect of control environment and financial performance as regard: Dahabshil has well elaborate organizational structure, through this system management are committed implementations of operations of the internal control system, management acts with a great degree of integrity in execution of their roles, ethical values are upheld in all management decisions in Dahabshil remittance. Frequencies of respondents were calculated to aid interpretation of the responses and the views elicited from respondents have been presented in below Table.

Table Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis		
Dimensions		Financial Performance
Control environment	Pearson correlation	.982
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.000
	N	80

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on the result of the table about the relationship between control environment and financial performance is investigated using Pearson correlation. The result obtain indicated that the control environment has significant and positive relationship with the financial performance given [r=0.982 N=80 P<0.000]. This result means the high of the control environment is the high of the financial performance and it's vice versa.

=Null hypothesis two: There is no relationship between control activities and the financial performance

of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu

In an effort to reach effective conclusion to the above research hypothesis The researcher looked at the effect of control activities on financial performance as regards: through this system Dahabshil has separation of roles within the organization, supervision by senior staff, staff are trained to implement accounting and financial management system and restriction of access to valuable information in the organization. The researcher also used the following descriptive statistics to analyze and interpret some questions related to control activities of Dahabshil Remittance Company.

Table 4.16 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis		
Dimensions		Financial Performance
Control activities	Pearson correlation	.734
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000
	N	80

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According the above table shows that there is a relationship between the effect of control activities on the financial performance at [$r = 0.734\%$, $P = .000$]. However, the significance of control activities on financial performance is very high. The above table showed that the internal control activity is significant related to the financial performance. The implication of this is that Dahabshil remittance more invests in internal control activities to improve performance of the company. In conclusion, there is a strong and positive relationship between control activity and financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company.

Null hypothesis three: There is no relationship between internal audit and the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu

The researcher also used the following descriptive statistics to analyse and interpret some questions related to internal audit of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu.

Table 4.22 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis		
Dimensions		Financial Performance
Internal audit	Pearson correlation	.386
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As the above table demonstrates, there is a weak relationship between internal audit on financial performance [$r = .386$, $p = .000$]. The results in the above table show that there is a weak relationship between effect internal audits on financial performance. The implication of this is that Dahabshil managers don't concentrate importance of internal audit activities in order to improve its financial performance of the company.

Summary of result

The main objective of this study was to determine whether there is no relationship between internal control systems and financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu-Somalia. The following table indicates that the most contributed factor was controlling environment which includes integrity and ethical values of personnel responsible for creating, administering, and monitoring the controls, commitment and competence of persons performing assigned duties, the extent of their independence from management, experience & stature, management philosophy and operating style, and Organizational structure (which may be a well-organized structure that provides for proper planning, directing and controlling operations and second factor contributed was control activities as shown table .

Table Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.988a	.976	.976	2.46679	.976	384.406	1	78	.000
2	.994b	.987	.987	1.79932	.011	84.555	1	77	.000

a. Predictor :(Constant), Environment

b. Predictor: (Constant), Environment, Activities

From the above model summary revealed that control environment was the only predictor of internal control systems that affect the financial performance in Dahabshil remittance. The relationship between the effect of control environment on the financial performance at $r = 98.8\%$, $P = .000$. The other remaining of 1.2% may be attributed to other factors. The effect of control environment on the financial performance is 97.6% at the level of sample. When generalized to population, the effect is 97.6%. The results in the above table pointed out that null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted and that is; there is a significant relationship between control environments to the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company. This is because the value of significance is less than 0.05 which indicates that the results were statistically

significant. However, the significance of Control environment on financial performance is very high 100%. Also the table shows that there is significant relationship between control activities and financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company. Thus, the null hypothesis which is there is no significant relationship between control activities and financial performance is rejected. Coefficient of determination explains the extent to which changes in the dependent variable can be explained by the change in the internal control systems variables on the percentage of variation in the dependent variable (financial performance) that is explained by all the independent variables such as control environment, control activities and internal audit relating to the financial performance. From the Table above also revealed that the two null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative is acceptable. This means that the most significant factor is control environment on the financial performance because $\{r = 98.8\%, P = .000\}$. This therefore means that other factors not studied in this research contribute 1.2% of variance in the dependent variable. The model above data means that if the company wants to improve its financial performance, it should concentrate on control environment more than other systems of internal control.

Conclusion

The effect of Control environment on Financial Performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu. Based on the findings of the study, the respondents revealed that Dahabshil control environment was having a significant relationship with the financial performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company. The researcher found that there is well elaborate organizational structure in Dahabshil remittance, management are committed implementation of operations of the internal control system in Dahabshil remittance, Dahabshil managers act with a great degree of integrity in execution of their roles, ethical values are upheld in all management decisions in Dahabshil remittance, all these environmental issues has a positive effect on the financial performance. In this regard it has been learnt that Dahabshil has heavily emphasized internal control environments as more other than variables because this indicator became the most predictable parameter compared to the other dimensions of the study.

The effect of Control activities on Financial Performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu. It is concluded that Dahabshil has an effective internal control system as supported by the study findings, Dahabshil has manipulative it's employees and give them with a clear separation of roles within the organization, there is proper supervision of junior staff at Dahabshil Remittance Company, staff are trained to implement accounting and financial management system and it is impossible for one staff to have access to all valuable information without the consent of senior staff. In this regard it has been learnt from the findings of the study that Dahabshil has successfully implemented and emphasized its internal control activities and it's actually yielded the expected results which was to improve its financial performance.

The effect of Internal Audit on Financial Performance of Dahabshil Remittance Company in Mogadishu. It can be concluded that the majority of the respondents revealed that internal audit was the poorest indicator of internal control system variables and It has been learnt from the findings of the study that there are challenges in the implementation of internal control system especially considering that internal audit department of

Dahabshil remittance has not sufficient staff, internal audit staff doesn't conducts regular internal audit activities of the remittance, internal audit report doesn't address weaknesses in the internal control system of Dahabshil remittance, Dahabshil management doesn't give autonomy to their internal auditors when performing their duties, and the last internal auditor report doesn't makes appropriate recommendations to management of company. It's also further concluded that the internal audit did not predict the relationship between internal control system and financial performance in Dahabshil remittance as it's completely excluded as predictors.

Recommendations

Dahabshil management should create an audit committee included board members independent of management. Such committee should be responsible for receiving internal audit reports and ensuring that management implements such reports. The appraisal and promotion of internal auditors should be the responsibility of the committee other than management. The existence of audit committee ensures independence of internal audit department can be improved the level of financial performance of the company. The researcher also recommended management of Dahabshil Remittance Company should improve its strategic financial performance and also the fees charged should match all costs incurring Dahabshil when performing its activities. Finally the researcher recommends that Dahabshil management should establish a strategy for improving the generation of additional finances for the operations of the organization and increasing its short term finance. Through this management could be done writing projects, other competitive endeavours which are directly aimed at winning funds for the company.

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